

Self Compassion in Adolescent Orphanages

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Abstract— *The purpose of this study was to examine the level of self compassion in adolescent orphanages. The study used a survey model involving 392 adolescents in orphanages in Medan and taken using accidental techniques. Data analysis uses descriptive statistics and one-way ANOVA. The results showed that the level of self compassion in adolescent orphanages was low. This finding could be used as a guide to further investigating the causes of low self compassion and making interventions in improving self compassion.*

Keywords— *Adolescent, orphanage, self-compassion.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In general, adolescents live with their parents, but not all children are fortunate to be able to live with family, among them must live in an orphanage. Poverty is the biggest reason children are in the Orphanage (Williamson & Greenberg, 2010). Triantoro (2005) explains that an orphanage is a place to care for orphans, even neglected children to be fostered into an independent, responsible, obedient and useful children for the community, homeland and nation. Hogi & Putra (2019) states that the orphanage is not only for orphans, but also for children who comes from a divorce family, children from low family economic factors, and disadvantaged children.

Adolescents who live in the orphanage have a tendency to more easily experience psychological pressure due to the feeling that other people are happier than themselves, feel wasted, lack of attention and affection, and also have demands to meet the strict rules in the orphanage (Kawitri, Rahmawati, Listiyandini & Rahmatika, 2018). An understanding of oneself in own goodness, self-limitation, complete awareness by not judging oneself, not isolating oneself and not overly criticizing oneself for self-deprivation is a definition of self compassion (Neff, 2003). Even the existence of a social label on themselves as "orphanage" makes them feel different from the others (Machmuroch & Hakim, 2015), but, adolescents with high self compassion can face that problem because they can treat someone and themselves well and understand human imperfections (Neff, 2011). Adolescents at the orphanage who have high self compassion tend to believe that they have something to be proud of, can learn to understand the condition of the family, do not consider others happier, do not wish if the family gather and do not feel alone (Nafisah, Hendriyani & Martiarini, 2018).

Neff (2011) mentions that there are 3 components contained in self compassion, namely self kindness, common humanity and mindfulness. Self kindness is an individual's tendency to nurture and provide an understanding of self when experiencing failure, suffering, or feeling inadequate in self rather than doing self-judgment hard (self-judgment). Common humanity makes individuals recognize that in every experience there will be failures and also successes that make him realize that he as a human being has limitations and far

from perfect words. Mindfulness is one's ability to develop self-awareness related to experiences experienced in a clear and balanced way.

Based from the description above, the researchers are interested to see the level of self-compassion in the orphanage adolescents.

II. OBJECTIVE AND METHOD

The main objective of this study was to examine the level of self compassion in adolescent orphanages in Medan. Subjects were 392 adolescents who came from 5 Orphanages in Medan, aged 13-18 years, samples taken using accidental techniques. Self-compassion measured by using the self compassion scale from Neff (2003) which has been adapted to Indonesian language and culture by Kawitri, Rahmawati, Listiyandini & Rahmatika (2018). The self compassion scale consists of 12 items. This scale uses a Likert scale model consisting of favorable and unfavorable statements with five alternative choices of answers: almost never, rarely, sometimes, often, and almost always. The scores moved from 1 to 5, The data were analyzed by descriptive statistic and one way Anova.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained in this study were 160 adolescents (40.8%) had low self compassion, 152 adolescents (38.8%) had moderate self compassion and 80 adolescents (20.4%) had high self compassion. Individuals with low self compassion tend to build self-criticism and judge themselves harshly for weaknesses, feel themselves to be imperfect and overemphasize the negative aspects (Neff, 2003).

The lowest self-compassion in life periods occurs in adolescence (Neff, 2011). Neff & McGehee (2010) say that unstable emotions which are one of the adolescence's characteristics phase, have a relationship with the frequent of criticizing themselves excessively or judging themselves against social comparisons with others. Similarly, adolescents who come from low economic backgrounds also tend to view themselves negatively and compare themselves with others regarding the status they have (Sünbül & Güneri, 2019). Most of the adolescents in orphanages come from low economic backgrounds (Williamson & Greenberg, 2010).

Neff (2003) explains that self-compassion make individuals aware about what they experience in undesirable circumstances, so that individuals are able to accept and not avoid the conditions that must be faced. Self compassion also includes self-understanding without judgment of one's own failures or incapacity. The experience of suffering is seen as part of human experience in general (Neff, 2003). Furthermore, Neff (2011) explains some of the benefits by the

existence of self compassion, such as being the most powerful medium for dealing with difficult situations so that individuals avoid the destructive emotions (Neff, 2011).

IV. CONCLUSION

This study presents a descriptive assessment of the level of self compassion in adolescents orphanage in Medan. This study revealed that 160 adolescents (40.8%) had low self compassion, 152 adolescents (38.8%) had moderate self compassion and 80 adolescents (20.4%) had high self compassion. These findings can be used as a guide to further investigate the causes of self compassion and make interventions to improve self compassion.

REFERENCES

- [1] Williamson, J., & Greenberg, A. (2010, September). Families, not orphanages. *Better Care Network*, 1-26. Diunduh dari https://www.thinkchildsafe.org/thinkbeforevisiting/resources/FamiliesNotOrphanages_J_Williamson.pdf
- [2] Triantoro, S. (2005). *Autis pemahaman baru untuk hidup bermakna bagi orang tua*. Jakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- [3] Hugo, E. & Putra, A.I. (2019). Kepribadian ekstrasversi dan kesepian pada remaja panti asuhan. *Jurnal Ilmiah Psikologi Terapan*, 7(1), 28-40. Doi: 10.22219/jipt.v7i1.7349
- [4] Kawitri, A.Z., Rahmatika, B.D., Listiyandini, A., & Rahmatika, R. (2018). Hubungan antara self-compassion dengan resiliensi pada remaja di panti asuhan. Prosiding dalam Konferensi Nasional Psikologi. *Jurnal Psikogenesis*, 7(1), 76-83. Doi: 10.24854/jps.v7i1.879
- [5] Machmuroch, R. N & Hakim, M. A. (2015). Pengaruh pelatihan pengenalan diri terhadap peningkatan harga diri remaja Panti Asuhan Pamardi Yoga Surakarta. *Jurnal Wacana Psikologi*, 7(2), 1-14. Diunduh dari <http://jurnalwacana.psikologi.fk.uns.ac.id/index.php/wacana/article/view/86>
- [6] Neff, K. (2003). Self-compassion: An alternative conceptualization of a healthy attitude toward oneself. *Self and Identity*, 2(2), 85-101. Doi:10.1080/15298860309032
- [7] Neff, K. D. (2011). Self-Compassion, self-esteem, and well-being. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 5(1), 1-12. Doi:10.1111/j.1751-9004.2010.00330.x
- [8] Neff, K. D., & McGehee, P. (2010). Self-compassion and Psychological Resilience Among Adolescents and Young Adults. *Self and Identity*, 9(3), 225-240. doi:10.1080/15298860902979307
- [9] Sünbül, Z. A, & Güneri, O. Y. (2019). The relationship between mindfulness and resilience: The mediating role of self compassion and emotion regulation in a sample of underprivileged Turkish adolescents. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 139, 337-342. Doi:10.1016/j.paid.2018.12.00